

INTERFACE IN SILICON CARBIDE WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

L.Cao, L.Geng, C.K.Yao and T.C.Lei
(Department of Metals and Technology, Harbin
Institute of Technology, Harbin, China)

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the whisker-matrix interface in a SiCw/Al composite with volume fraction of whisker (V_f) of 22% was studied. By Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) we found that almost all the SiC whiskers were coated with matrix aluminium and that the SiC whiskers were bonded perfectly with the aluminium matrix. The STEM observation results show that the interaction between the SiC whisker and the aluminium (including the interface reaction and diffusion) was in the range of 50 nm.

INTRODUCTION

The whisker-matrix interface in a SiCw/Al composite is one of the main factors influencing the properties of the composite, or even the most important factor in some cases^{1,2}. Three kinds of mechanisms have been pointed out for the bonding of the interface between the SiC whisker and the aluminium: 1. SiO₂ thin layer was formed at the interface; 2. There is no special phase at the interface; 3. Al₄C₃ thin layer existed at the interface. All the recent studies show that there is neither SiO₂ nor Al₄O₃ at the SiCw-Al interface. By means of Auger probe analyzing and X-ray spectrum measuring, Arsenault and Pande³ proposed that aluminium had diffused into the SiC whisker through the interface and that the diffusion distance was much higher than the calculated value. In this paper, the Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) and STEM were used to observe and measure the bonding, reaction and diffusion of the whisker-matrix interface of a SiCw/Al composite.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in this research was a SiCw/6061 Al composite produced by a squeeze casting method⁴. The volume fraction of the whisker (V_f) is 22%. In order to analyze the interface in the SiCw/Al composite, the small notched cylindrical specimens (shown in Fig.1) were tested in a PHI-600 Scanning Auger Microprobe. The specimens were broken in situ in the tester in a high vacuum of 1.13×10^{-7} Pa, and then the elemental contents of the fracture surface were measured. The change of elemental contents of the fracture surface after being sputter etched were measured.

The specimens used for TEM observation were made by sputter etching. The elemental contents at the interface between the matrix and the

Fig.1 The specimen for Auger microprobe analysis (mm)

whisker, both perpendicular and parallel to the observing direction, were measured. In order to decrease the effect of the shape of the SiC whisker the direction of the electron beam was chosen to be the [111] direction of the transverse whisker before measuring the elemental contents. The spatial resolution of the energy dispersive X-ray analysis is about 30 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fracture surface of the SiCw/Al composite is different from that of the long fiber reinforced composite⁵. Almost all the pulled-out whiskers in the fracture surface of the SiCw/Al composite are coated with Al from the matrix⁶. This conclusion is further supported by Auger microprobe measuring of the fracture surface.

From Fig.2(a) it can be seen that the spectral intensity of Al at the analyzed point is higher and that of Si, C and Mg at the point is lower, which means that there is little Si, C and Mg, and which can be considered to be micro-alloy or inclusion in the matrix. Because Al is easily oxidized, the elemental oxygen in the specimen room can be absorbed on the fracture surface. The fact that the Auger spectrum of alumina and that of the elemental oxygen is different makes it possible to decide whether alumina or elemental oxygen causes the appearance of oxygen intensity in the spectra. By comparing the measured spectrum with the standard one, it was decided that the elemental oxygen instead of

(a) A result of spot analyzing before sputter.

(b) A result of spot analyzing after sputtering for 2 min.

(c) A result of spot analyzing after sputtering for 67 min.

(d) A result of line scanning analyzing after sputtering for 67 min.

Fig. 2 The Auger microprobe analysis of the fracture surface of the SiCw/Al composite.

the alumina causes the oxygen intensity. This conclusion is coincident with the results of reference 7. Fig. 2(b) showed that the oxygen intensity disappeared from the spectrum of the fracture surface after being sputter etched for 2 min. This conclusion further supports the result that the oxygen in the fracture surface is absorbed from the air in the specimen room. Fig. 2(e) shows that in the spectrum of the fracture surface after being sputter etched for 67 min, there was obvious spectral intensity of C and Si. This indicated that the SiC whisker had been exposed. In order to further prove this conclusion, a line scanning analysis through the measured point was carried out and the results were shown in Fig. 2(d). From Fig. 2(d) it can be seen that the peaks of Si and C are in the same poace where the content of aluminium is the lowest. This result suggests that the bonding between the SiC whisker and the aluminium matrix is quite good.

The observed TEM results are presented in Fig.3. Fig. 3(a) and Fig.3(b) show the longitudinal and transverse SiC whiskers, respectively. In both cases no interfacial reaction layer was found. It can be seen from Fig. 3(b) that almost all the aluminium grains have grown from one or two sides of the hexagonal SiC whisker. This seems to indicate that there are certain orientation relationships between the SiC whisker and the matrix. The results of spectral analysis across the SiC whisker-aluminium interface are presented in Fig.4. Fig.4(a) is a case of a longitudinal whisker. In the range of 150 nm around the interface there is a concentration gradient of aluminium. However, this dose not mean that the aluminium has diffused into the SiC whisker, and the reasons are the following: 1. the effect of the matrix aluminium on the results near the interface is higher than that at the centre of the whisker; 2. the drift of the specimen or probe has some effect on the results; 3. the geometrical shape of the SiC whisker can cause the part of the whisker near the interface to be coated with aluminium, which will results in the distortion of the results. If transverse SiC whisker are used for measuring, the effect of the third reason can be lowered. If the [111] direction is the observing direction, the normal line of the side planes of the whisker will be in the (111) plane. Fig. 4(b) shows the elemental distribution near the interface between the transverse SiC whisker and the matrix aluminium. From this figure it can be seen that the compositions in both whisker and matrix are unchanged, and in the range of 50nm near the interface there is a mutation in composition. This means that the interaction between the SiC whisker and the matrix aluminium (including the interface reaction and diffusion) has only taken place in the range of 50 nm. The Si content in the matrix is coincident with that in the aluminium alloy, so it can be considered that no Si can diffuse into the matrix, and as a result of this no C can diffuse into the matrix. It is noted that the weight fraction of aluminium in the SiC whisker is higher than 10%. The reasons may be the effect of the aluminium near the whisker or that the surface of the SiC whisker is coated by some aluminium during the production of the specimen.

It is easy to understand the fact that no aluminium has diffused into the SiC whisker. the β -SiC whisker used in this research was a covalent compound with the lattice structure of FCC and atomic ratio of 1:1, so in a normal case it is impossible for other atoms to diffuse into the SiC whisker. According to the follow equation³:

$$X = \sqrt{Dt} \quad (1)$$

where X is diffusion length, D is diffusion coefficient and t is diffusion time, the diffusion length of the aluminium in the SiC whisker at 773 K is only 0.1 μm for one year. This indicates that it is impossible for the aluminium to diffuse into the SiC whisker.

(a) Longitudinal whisker.

(b) Transverse whisker (observing direction is in the [111] direction).

Fig.3 The TEM micrograph of SiCw/Al composite.

(a) Longitudinal whisker.

(b) Transverse whisker.

Fig.4 The STEM EDXA analysis of SiCw/Al composite.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The bonding between the SiC whisker and the aluminium matrix is quite good. There are certain orientation relationships between the SiC whisker and the aluminium matrix.
2. There is no interface reaction layer in the SiCw/Al composite.
3. Neither Si nor C can diffuse into the aluminium matrix through the interface, and Al can not diffuse into the SiC whisker.

REFERENCES

1. R.L.Mehan and R.B.Bolon, J.Mat. Sci., Vol. 14, 10(1979), P. 2471.
2. I.H.Kahn, Met. Trans., Vol. 7A (1982), P. 1281.
3. R.J. Arsenault and C. S. Pande, Scr. Metall., Vol. 18 (1984), P. 1131.
4. L.Geng, L.Cao, W. Zhao and C.K. Yao, MRS, IMAM, Tokyo, (1988).
5. G. H. Han, L.Cao, L. Geng and C.K. Yao, Composites, Vol. 18, 5(1987), P. 400.
6. L. Cao et al., MRS, IMAM, Tokyo, (1988).
7. T.G.Nieh, J. Wadsworth and D.J. Chellmann, Scr. Metall., Vol. 19, (1985), P. 181.